

The first move in a drawing tic-tac-toe is always optimal

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We prove that the first move of a drawing tic-tac-toe is always optimal.

Let S be a nonempty finite set, whose members are called the **squares**, and \mathcal{W} a set of nonempty subsets of S , called the **winning sets**, such that $S = \bigcup \mathcal{W}$. A **tic-tac-toe on \mathcal{W}** is a game with the following rules played by Alice and Bob:

Alice and Bob pick alternately *distinct* squares, starting with Alice. Say that Alice picks a_1 , Bob picks a_2 , Alice picks a_3 , and so on. If a_t belongs to a winning set W and t is odd, we say that Alice **blocks** W from time t on. Similarly, if a_t belongs to a winning set W and t is even, we say that Bob **blocks** W from time t on.

The game stops as soon as one of the following events occurs:

- (a) the set $\{a_1, a_3, \dots, a_t\}$ (with t odd) contains some winning set,
- (b) the set $\{a_2, a_4, \dots, a_t\}$ (with t even) contains some winning set,
- (c) each winning set is blocked by Alice and Bob.

In case (a) **Alice wins**, in case (b) **Bob wins**, in case (c) it is a **draw**.

The following Theorem is well known:

Theorem 1. *Bob cannot have a winning strategy.*

I've seen many proofs of this fact², but I don't understand them. The purpose of this text is to spell out such a proof. In fact we will prove a slightly stronger statement, which is:

Theorem 2. *If Alice's first move gives Bob a winning strategy, then Alice had a winning strategy (which she spoiled).*

In particular:

Corollary 3. *If our tic-tac-toe is a draw, then Alice's first move is necessarily optimal (in the sense that she has a drawing strategy starting with any given move).*

Suppose we have a draw. If Alice (resp. Bob) blocks all winning sets before Bob (resp. Alice) does, we say that **Alice draws before Bob** (resp. **Bob draws before Alice**).

Theorem 4. *If Alice's first move gives Bob a strategy for winning or drawing before Alice, then Alice had a strategy for winning or drawing before Bob.*

In particular:

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²Like the proof of Theorem C.2 page 683 in József Beck's book **Combinatorial Games: Tic-Tac-Toe Theory**.

If $a'_2 \neq a_1$, then $\Sigma(S; a_1; b_1; a'_2)$ is equivalent to $\Sigma(S \setminus \{b_1, a'_2\}; a_1; b_2; a'_3)$.

If $a'_2 = a_1$, then $\Sigma(S; a_1; b_1; a'_2)$ is equivalent to $\Sigma(S \setminus \{a_1, b_1\}; a_2; b_2; a'_3)$.

Since $|S \setminus \{b_1, a'_2\}| = |S \setminus \{a_1, b_1\}| = |S| - 2$, the proof is complete. \square

This completes the proof of Part 1 of Theorem 2. \square

Proof of Theorem 2, Part 2. There is a least i such that $\{b_1, \dots, b_i\}$ contains some winning set. Then $\{a_1, \dots, a_i\}$ contains no winning set. Thus $\{b'_1, \dots, b'_i\}$ contains some winning set but, in view of (3), $\{a'_2, \dots, a'_i\}$ does not. This implies (2) and completes the proof of the Theorem. \square

Proof of Theorem 4, Part 1. Same as Proof of Theorem 2, Part 1. \square

Proof of Theorem 4, Part 2. In the case when Bob wins, we show that B' wins by arguing exactly as in Proof of Theorem 2, Part 2. \square

Proof of Theorem 4, Part 3. Assume that Bob draws before Alice. We must show that B' wins or draws before A' . There is a least i such that $\{b_1, \dots, b_i\}$ meets all winning sets. Then $\{a_1, \dots, a_i\}$ does not meet all winning sets. In view of (3) this implies that $\{b'_1, \dots, b'_i\}$ meets all winning sets and $\{a'_2, \dots, a'_i\}$ does not. As a result, B' wins or draws before A' . This completes the proof of the Theorem. \square